

A Study of the Agile Coach's Role

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1 Interview Guideline

1. Asking demographic information:
 - Current role
 - Years of working in this role
 - Previous role
 - Education
 - Years of working experience (any work)
 - Number of the teams
 - Size of the team(s)
2. Who are your clients (development teams, organization management, etc)?
3. Do you work with teams that are in between agile transformation or with teams that are already applying agile principles but need help? If so, what are their problems?
4. Are you working with your teams in face-to-face interactions or are you coaching them remotely? What are the biggest differences when working with both types of teams?
5. How does the team find you?
6. Do you also use coaching?
 - How does Agile Coaching take place, is there a framework, phases that you follow, when starting with a new team?
 - Which methods do you use when coaching?
 - How long does the coaching take place? (The period of coaching for one team)
 - What are the challenges that you are facing while coaching?
 - How have you solved the challenges?
7. How has your role developed/changed?
8. Who are the people that you work the most with, stakeholders?
9. Who is an Agile Coach in your mind?
10. What kind of competencies do you have to have, in order to be a successful Agile Coach?
11. What is the impact of the Agile Coach?
12. How does the team/organization know that you have been successful?
13. How is that role valued in the company?
14. What do you enjoy the most about the role?